

Assessment for inclusive student-centred learning

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3.1 Introduction

An essential element of any educational change or implementation is the assessment practice. Especially for the implementation of inclusive student-centred teaching faculty have to reflect and design assessment practices in which all students get ample opportunities to show their progress.

3.1.1 Relevance to Inclusive student-centred learning

Inclusive student-centred practices are complex, encompassing a variation of learning objectives, pedagogical approaches, and instructional techniques. In a European-wide project (COALITION, 2023), inclusive teaching is placed at the centre of all learning and teaching at our universities. We make the premise that quality higher education pedagogy can emerge from the aim of teaching for diverse student needs (Hunt & Chalmers, 2021) and should be seen as an additive to 'good teaching' at university (Hellstén, 2008). The current understanding of student 'learning-centeredness' implies a holistic approach to what higher education teaching and learning ought to deliver in current times. It goes beyond mere skills development for future employability (Denman & Hellstén, 2022) or the decoding of current artificial intelligibilities of machine learning. Universities are currently struggling with the task, that some might consider undesirable, of redefining their learning and teaching ethos for a generation of learners who are not necessarily devoted to learning in the 'traditional' ways (Denman et al., 2023). This undeniably brings forth a number of issues about what, how, when, and where it is appropriate to consider inclusivity in higher education assessment practices.

In order to set out an approach for the future of inclusive assessment in higher education, particularly in Europe, we turn to a comparative approach within and across cultural, national, economic, and political spheres. We begin with considering assessment as a *cultural practice* which also makes it necessary to recognise considerations of the taken-for-grantedness (Ninnes & Hellstén, 2004) of cultural 'know-how' and the specificity that is implied in the assessment, evaluation, examination, appreciation, and recognition of academic knowledge and skills. The obligation of cultural know-how in all assessment activities might, in light of artificial intelligence, currently be considered as 'old school'. For example, including names from different places around the world, examples of visuals including personas from a range of cultures, identities, and ethnicities. Or using language in the learning tasks that can promote a sense of belonging for a broad variety of our students. This in turn will lead to an increase in motivation for student learning, achievement, and retention.

However, our everyday observations insistently show that in many university lecture halls and seminar spaces mainstreaming is still the cultural default. Is it the case that when we paint a picture of pedagogy, we go with the mainstream? For example, when we nominate case examples in assessments or assignments, do we readily use local names such as 'Emma' and 'John', rather than 'Unna' and 'Aslak', or do we more often use traditional family and gender roles in examples and case descriptions rather than opting for LGBTQIA+ examples? How many university course examinations allow for the assessment task to be written, e.g. in the native language of the student authors (Petocz & Reid, 2008)? Can we imagine an assessment culture grounded in the diversity of student backgrounds within our cohorts? When it comes to inclusive learning, our know-how about different cultures makes a big difference to what is learnt and how it is learnt.

Most university assessment policies and practices are tied to a national accreditation system that regulates what is to be learnt and the criteria by which the learning outcomes are assessed (Hunt & Chalmers, 2021). Most

assessment practices are designed to adhere to the national regulations. The task of inclusive student-centred pedagogies becomes one in which academic freedom and scientific evidence-based knowledge inform the pedagogical decision-making and agency of faculty.

3.2 Issues and examples of inclusive assessment practices in higher education

3.2.1 Assessment as a reflection of cultural values

Positioned within an inclusive higher education setting, faculty need to recognise how different identities, cultural, ethnic, generational, gender, and others, influence student learning and ways of expressing their learning. Examples of inclusive assessment practices show that any inclusive assessment starts with the awareness and understanding the diversity of values and understandings of what we mean by knowledge, learning, and achievement. For example:

- Some cultures might value oral communication and narrativity as a source of knowledge, while others might question the validity of the oral form of knowledge.
- Some cultures have ways of conceptualizing knowledge (e.g., relational, holistic) that may be overlooked or ignored in current higher education assessment approaches that tend to prioritise individualistic forms of learning and assessment (Buchanan & Hellstén, 2020).

By framing assessment as a cultural practice, educators are supported to examine how current assessment practices may inadvertently privilege certain norms while marginalizing others. Inclusive assessment practices aim to acknowledge the various ways of knowing, understand diversity as the essence of our who we are (Nieminen, 2022; Tai et al., 2021; Tai et al., 2022). Therefore, educators as designers of assessment practices must understand how current norms and values can impact student learning and assessment. Consequently, inclusive assessment practices should aim to accommodate various ways of knowledge sharing, and to some extent challenge, or disrupt contemporary educational practice.

3.2.2 Assessment practices as inclusive heuristics

In higher education, assessments are also used to navigate students into the disciplinary cultures, values, and expectations of the academic communities. These practices go beyond the measuring of learning to reinforce specific sanctioned cultural ideas about merit, discipline, and competence (Foucault, 1961).

- While assuming objectivity (Denman, 2019), standardised testing can become inadvertently culturally biased, exemplifying a narrow view of knowledge and understanding that may not always account for the nuanced ways in which students might wish to define and express themselves.
- Inclusive pedagogy should therefore promote the use of formative assessments (with continuous feedback on the learning process and ample opportunities for reflective practices) over mere summative assessment (involving judgment). This will prevent the undesirable practice and side effects of penalising students who do not perform well amidst high-stress, or time-pressured environments. These students may demonstrate deeper understanding through formative assessment methods (Denman & Hellsten 2022).

In short, higher education assessment should be a tool not just for judging academic achievement and up-skilling, but also for diagnosing the learning process, helping students regulate their own learning, and facilitating their belonging and cultural integration into academic life (Denman & Hellstén, 2022).

3.2.1 Comparing power dimensions of inclusivity

Assessment in inclusive higher education should involve recognising the disciplinary and academic power subtleties at play. Assessment practices are never neutral, they reflect national accreditation frameworks and institutional impact structures that define preferential types of knowledge and how these are sanctioned.

- Some students may face systemic barriers, or inequity and inequality, that prevent them from performing well on traditional assessments, for example, those students with neurodiverse abilities, non-native speaking students, students with family care, or students from first (in family) generation university students (cf. Thomas & McCormick, 2017). Acknowledging inclusive assessment as an embedded cultural exercise brings attention to the systematic barriers students may experience and how assessment practices should be changed and adjusted to provide more equitable opportunities for showing achievement.
- Many students in today's university cohorts are new to higher education teaching and learning and have no social or academic compass for orienting themselves in the academic community (Curtis, 2020). Therefore, cultural inclusion in assessment practices should involve creating alternative and innovative forms of assessment, such as portfolios, project presentations, or collaborative assessments, which provide opportunities for deep engagement, aligned with the cultural values and learning preferences, for all students.

3.2.4 Engaging in communities of assessment practices

Cultural practice involves reciprocal engagement, and in inclusive higher education, this can be enacted by considering students as co-creators of the assessment process. This may include:

- Incorporating the student voice in the development of assessment criteria, by allowing for reflection on the alignment of assessments with students' learning processes.
- Involving students' participation in self-assessment and peer assessment. Such participation can encourage an exchange of ideas about learning, which will enhance understanding and respect for diversity (Reierstam & Hellstén, 2021).

3.2.5 Linking the world in inclusive assessment

Current globalized academic environments each have different cultural and linguistic practices in assessment. Especially international students can often find themselves in new unfamiliar educational and academic communities where the approach to learning and assessment deviates from what they are used to. Comparing the differences between various assessment practices can help faculty adopt assessment practices that support a broad range of learning approaches:

- In an inclusive teaching and learning setting, assessment should have a flexible format in order to anticipate variations in learning preferences. For example, in Sweden, group work, discussion forums, and collaborative learning tasks are, by many students, appreciated more than individual tasks.

Assessment methods are not neutral or universally applicable. Rather, they are embedded in cultural contexts that reflect values, assumptions, hierarchies, and power dimensions. To make assessment inclusive, it is important to design assessment heuristics that can account for cultural and linguistic diversity, promote academic equity, cater to neurodiverse students, and accommodate the ways students with various backgrounds and identities engage with and validate their learning. This approach not only enhances the fairness and relevance of inclusive assessments but also nurtures a more inclusive, diverse academic environment that values all students' learning potential and capabilities.

3.3 Faculty perspectives

All faculty involved in assessment practices should be aware that they have agency to make their assessment practices inclusive. It may be difficult for faculty to refrain from imposing one's own cultural values and assumptions when evaluating student work. But, when educators feel culturally knowledgeable about their own reflective selves, they will welcome and appreciate the diversity of their students' input into the learning context and assessment experiences. Continuous inclusive and reflective practice (cf. Schön, 1992) helps in seeking to minimize one's own bias, by ensuring that assessment practices are fair and equitable across diverse groups of students. A collective cultural and linguistic literacy will have a positive influence on how assessment is organised, designed, delivered, and interpreted by both students and faculty. In other words, inclusive assessment builds new pathways to the co-creation of learning and assessment methods in higher education.

3.4 Resources and illustrative examples

3.4.1 *Assessment rubric co-creation and personalization*

Including student voices in the development of assessment criteria can be one way of making an assessment more inclusive. Literature on the development of assessment rubrics suggests that co-creating rubrics with students can have several benefits (Andrade, 2005; Reddy & Andrade, 2010). Based on the review of stronger and weaker examples of previous student work, students can suggest (new) assessment criteria for their own work. This can help them in becoming more familiar with and getting a deeper understanding of both the assignment goals as well as the assessment criteria (Andrade, 2000). Furthermore, involving students in the development of assessment rubrics can also allow for some degree of personalisation. For example, at Leiden University, some programs allow students to add personalised assessment criteria to an otherwise standardised assignment rubric. Such an addition allows the faculty member to also assess the attainment of learning objectives that are specific to an individual student (or a group of students in the case of a group assignment).

3.4.2 *Two-stage exams*

The importance of group work, and collaborative learning in inclusive teaching practice has been noted throughout this chapter. One particularly interesting format in this regard is the idea of the two-stage exam (Gilley & Clarkston, 2014). In a two-stage exam, students first engage in an assessment activity individually. Then, after handing in an individual answer sheet, they retake the same exam in a small group setting. The second-stage group exam allows students to discuss and compare different answer options with each other. Especially for multiple choice-type exams, the two-stage exam has shown great potential concerning peer learning and deep elaborative processing (Gilley & Clarkston, 2014; Levy et al., 2023). We could also regard two-stage exams as an inclusive assessment practice. Students who are not familiar with a certain exam format can learn much from students who already have experience with the test format. For example, students can learn how to best approach an unfamiliar exam format and the types of problem-solving required to do well. Two-stage exams are sometimes implemented as summative (graded) exams (e.g., Gilley & Clarkston, 2014). However, there are also examples of formative (ungraded) two-stage exams. For instance, during the COALITION project, at the University of Crete, a two-stage exam for a formative assessment was developed and successfully implemented. Likewise, at the Leiden University medical department, some faculty implemented a two-stage exam in the context of team-based learning (Gullo et al., 2015; Parmelee et al., 2012). In this particular setting, students engage in a so-called Readiness Assurance Test to activate prior knowledge before they start working on an in-class group assignment. The Readiness Assurance Test has a two-stage setup where students first take a test individually and then retake the same test in a small group. This allows for peer learning and ensures students start collaborating on the group assignment with comparable levels of prior knowledge.

3.5 References

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